

MEDICAL SCIENCES

MODERN APPROACHES AND PROSPECTIVE DIRECTIONS FOR THE TREATMENT OF GOUT

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Abstract

Gout is one of the most common types of inflammatory arthritis, the development of which is directly related to impaired purine metabolism and the accumulation of sodium monourate crystals in the tissues. In recent years, the understanding of the pathogenesis of this disease, as well as approaches to its treatment, has changed significantly. If earlier the main emphasis was on eliminating acute pain syndrome, then modern rheumatology is focused on long-term control of uric acid levels and preventing the formation of crystal deposits.

The aim of the work is to analyze current scientific data on the molecular mechanisms of gout development, the role of genetic factors, new diagnostic methods and current therapeutic strategies. Particular attention is paid to promising areas of treatment, including biological therapy, selective urate transporter inhibitors and experimental biotechnological methods.

The paper summarizes the results of modern clinical studies and international recommendations regarding the treatment of patients with gout. The significance of the NLRP3 inflammasome, interleukin 1 β , URAT1 and ABCG2 transporters in the development of the disease is considered. The Treat to Target concept, the safety of xanthine oxidase inhibitors, and the features of the therapy of refractory forms of gout are separately analyzed.

The obtained data confirm that effective management of patients with gout requires an individualized approach, long-term control of hyperuricemia, and consideration of concomitant cardiometabolic pathology.

Keywords: gout, hyperuricemia, uric acid, NLRP3, urate-lowering therapy, Treat to Target.

Introduction.

Gout is one of the most common chronic inflammatory joint diseases in the adult population. The prevalence of this pathology is increasing every year, which is largely due to the aging of the population, the increase in the incidence of obesity, metabolic syndrome and chronic kidney disease [1].

The modern understanding of gout has moved far beyond the traditional notion of “a disease of excessive meat consumption.” Gout is now considered a systemic metabolic and inflammatory disease, the basis of which is the deposition of sodium monourate crystals in various tissues of the body. Crystal deposits can form not only in the joints, but also in the tendons, kidneys, soft tissues, and vascular walls [3].

Chronic hyperuricemia is accompanied by persistent low-grade inflammation, which negatively affects the cardiovascular system and kidney function. That is why modern approaches to the treatment of gout are based not only on controlling symptoms, but also on eliminating the pathogenetic mechanisms of the disease [20].

The aim of the work is to systematize current data on the pathophysiology of gout, the latest diagnostic methods, and promising areas of therapy in accordance with the principles of evidence-based medicine.

Analysis of recent studies and publications

Current understanding of the pathogenesis of gout includes the role of the NLRP3 inflammasome and IL 1 β in the development of inflammation.

Thus, the key link in the development of gouty arthritis is the accumulation of sodium monourate crystals in the tissues. After their phagocytosis by innate

immune cells, the NLRP3 inflammasome is activated, a multiprotein complex that responds to intracellular stress [3].

Activation of the inflammasome is accompanied by the conversion of inactive pro-IL 1 β into biologically active interleukin 1 β . This cytokine plays a leading role in triggering the acute inflammatory process in gout. Under its influence, the synthesis of pro-inflammatory mediators is enhanced, neutrophil migration occurs, and a typical clinical attack of arthritis is formed [15].

Neutrophils accumulating in the focus of inflammation not only support tissue damage but also participate in further limiting the inflammatory response by forming extracellular neutrophil traps. However, prolonged retention of sodium monourate crystals leads to chronic inflammation with the formation of tophi and progressive joint damage [4].

Genetic factors are also one of the main mechanisms of hyperuricemia.

The leading factor in the development of gout is a persistent increase in uric acid levels. In most cases, hyperuricemia occurs as a result of impaired excretion of urate, rather than excessive synthesis [1].

The URAT1 and ABCG2 transporters, which regulate renal and intestinal excretion of uric acid, are of great importance. Genetically determined changes in the function of these proteins can significantly increase the risk of developing gout even in the absence of significant nutritional disorders [16].

The enzyme xanthine oxidase plays a significant role in the synthesis of uric acid. That is why xanthine

oxidase inhibitors remain the mainstay of modern urate-lowering therapy [4].

The data obtained suggest that dietary factors are only an additional risk component, while genetic mechanisms largely determine the predisposition to develop the disease.

Recent studies confirm the importance of a number of inflammatory and metabolic markers in predicting the course of gout. One of the most promising is calprotectin, a protein secreted by activated neutrophils and macrophages.

Elevated calprotectin levels are associated with more crystal deposits and higher inflammatory activity even in the inter-attack period [5].

Other potential biomarkers are also being actively investigated, including IL-6, TNFSF14, GlycA, soluble E-cadherin, and urinary metabolomics [12].

Traditional uric acid testing is not always sufficient to confirm the diagnosis of gout, which is why instrumental diagnostic methods are becoming increasingly important.

Ultrasound examination allows to detect the characteristic sign of "double contour", which indicates the deposition of crystals on the surface of the cartilage.

Dual-energy computed tomography allows to determine the localization and volume of urate deposits precisely. The method is especially valuable in patients with tophaceous or atypical forms of gout [8].

Despite the high informativeness of DECT, ultrasound remains a more accessible method in everyday clinical practice.

The modern strategy for the treatment of gout includes:

1. Treat to Target Concept

Modern gout therapy is based on the Treat to Target principle, which involves achieving and maintaining a stable target level of uric acid [2].

The solubility threshold for sodium monourate is considered to be a concentration of approximately 6.8 mg/dL. Exceeding this level promotes crystal formation and disease progression.

The main therapeutic goals are:

- less than 6 mg/dL for most patients;
- less than 5 mg/dL for severe tophaceous gout.

The lower the uric acid level that can be maintained, the faster the crystals dissolve and the lower the risk of recurrent exacerbations.

To achieve the therapeutic goal, gradual titration of allopurinol or febuxostat doses is often necessary, and in some cases, combination therapy [2].

2. Xanthine oxidase inhibitors and safety issues

Allopurinol and febuxostat are the mainstays of urate-lowering therapy. However, their cardiovascular safety has long been a subject of debate.

The CARES trial [20] demonstrated a possible increased risk of cardiovascular mortality with febuxostat in high-risk patients. However, the FAST Trial [11] did not show a significant increase in mortality. Given the available evidence, allopurinol remains the first-line drug, especially in patients with concomitant cardiovascular disease [13].

Before prescribing allopurinol in certain populations, it is recommended to determine the HLA B*5801

allele, the carriership of which is associated with the risk of severe hypersensitivity reactions [13].

In patients with chronic kidney disease, therapy should be initiated with minimal doses followed by gradual titration under laboratory control.

Treatment of refractory gout is carried out with the help of:

1. Pegloticase. Pegloticase is a recombinant pegylated uricase that converts uric acid to the more soluble allantoin. It is used in patients with severe refractory gout and significant tophi [14].

Pegloticase therapy provides rapid and significant reductions in uric acid levels, but its efficacy may be compromised by the development of antibodies to the drug.

Combination therapy with pegloticase and methotrexate is increasingly being used to reduce immunogenicity. This approach has been shown to increase clinical response rates and reduce the risk of infusion reactions [14].

2. IL 1 inhibitors. Since IL 1 β is a key mediator of gouty inflammation, the use of drugs that block this cytokine has become a promising direction.

Canakinumab, a monoclonal antibody to IL 1 β , is able to effectively reduce the severity of inflammation and the frequency of attacks.

Anakinra, which is an IL-1 receptor antagonist, is used mainly in complex clinical cases when standard therapy is contraindicated or insufficiently effective [15].

Promising directions of therapy for gout are:

1. SEL 212. SEL 212 is a combined therapeutic system that combines pegylated uricase and immunomodulatory nanoparticles ImmTOR. The main goal of this technology is to reduce the formation of antibodies to the enzyme and prolong the therapeutic effect. The results of clinical studies demonstrate a sustained reduction in uric acid levels, a decrease in the frequency of exacerbations and better tolerability compared to traditional uricase therapy [17].

2. Selective URAT1 inhibitors. Promising new-generation drugs include AR882 and epaminurad. These drugs block the URAT1 transporter and reduce urate reabsorption in the kidneys. Clinical studies have shown their high efficacy in patients with chronic and tophaceous gout. The advantage of the new selective inhibitors is a better tolerability profile compared to previous uricosuric drugs [9].

3. Gene therapy. One of the most innovative areas is considered to be gene therapy aimed at restoring uricase activity. The possibility of using viral vectors or mRNA technologies for long-term expression of the enzyme and stable control of uric acid levels is being considered. Despite significant potential, these methods are still in the early stages of research [7].

Gout is often associated with other metabolic and cardiovascular diseases, the most important of which are type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity, hypertension, chronic kidney disease, and atherosclerotic vascular lesions. The presence of such comorbid conditions significantly complicates the course of the disease and requires comprehensive interdisciplinary management of patients [20].

In recent years, sodium-glucose cotransporter type 2 (SGLT2) inhibitors have attracted considerable interest, and are mainly used in the treatment of diabetes mellitus. In addition to their hypoglycemic effect, drugs of this group have demonstrated the ability to influence purine metabolism and contribute to a moderate decrease in uric acid levels [10].

Clinical trials have shown that SGLT2 inhibitors are associated with a reduction in serum urate concentrations compared with placebo or other hypoglycemic agents. One possible mechanism for this effect is increased renal excretion of urate due to competitive inhibition of its reabsorption via the URAT1 and GLUT9 transporters in the proximal tubules. Additional roles may be played by changes in intrarenal hemodynamics and improved nephron function [8].

The practical significance of these effects is supported by real-world clinical evidence of reduced gout attacks in patients receiving SGLT2 inhibitors. The most significant benefit is seen in patients with a combination of gout, diabetes, and chronic kidney disease, as drugs in this group simultaneously provide nephro- and cardioprotective effects [19].

However, SGLT2 inhibitors cannot be considered as a stand-alone urate-lowering therapy. Their use should be evaluated only as an adjunct component of the complex treatment of patients with concomitant cardiometabolic disorders [12].

Modern research in the field of gout treatment is primarily aimed at overcoming the shortcomings of standard therapy, in particular, insufficient effectiveness in some patients and the development of adverse reactions. One of the most promising areas is considered to be the improvement of uricase therapy by creating combined biotechnological drugs [22].

An example of this approach is SEL-212, a combination of pegylated uricase and ImmTOR immunomodulatory nanoparticles. The main goal of this technology is to reduce the formation of neutralizing antibodies to the enzyme, which are the main cause of loss of efficacy of biological therapy. Data from phase II–III clinical trials demonstrate longer maintenance of low uric acid levels and a lower incidence of infusion reactions compared with traditional pegloticase therapy [18].

Despite the promise of such methods, safety concerns remain. The main risks include immune reactions, infusion complications, and the potential consequences of excessive uric acid lowering, which may be accompanied by oxidative stress. In addition, data on the long-term effects of long-term intervention in purine metabolism are still lacking [7].

Another promising direction is the development of new generation selective URAT1 inhibitors, in particular AR882 and epaminurad. These drugs provide a more pronounced reduction in urate levels by blocking their reabsorption in the kidneys. Compared with previous uricosuric agents, they are characterized by better selectivity and a more favorable tolerability profile [16].

However, the final assessment of the safety of these drugs requires further studies, especially regard-

ing their effects on renal function, the risk of nephrolithiasis, and use in patients with severe cardiovascular or metabolic diseases [19].

In parallel, experimental approaches related to gene therapy are actively developing. The main idea is to restore uricase activity using viral vectors or modern mRNA technologies. Although such methods have significant potential, they remain in the early stages of research due to the risks of uncontrolled gene expression and possible immunological complications [6].

Thus, further development of gout therapy depends not only on the creation of new molecules, but also on the accumulation of evidence of their long-term efficacy and safety. The use of biologics and recombinant enzymes has been an important advance in the treatment of severe gout. However, along with their high efficacy, these methods are accompanied by a number of complex problems related to the safety of therapy [21].

One of the main obstacles is immunogenicity - the ability of the drug to induce the formation of antibodies. The formation of anti-drug antibodies can not only reduce the effectiveness of treatment, but also contribute to the development of serious infusion reactions. Modern approaches involve the use of combination therapy with low doses of immunomodulators, which allows suppressing the excessive immune response and increasing the duration of the therapeutic effect [7].

An additional problem is the increased risk of infections due to the blockade of pro-inflammatory cytokines, primarily IL-1. Elderly patients, patients with chronic renal failure, and individuals with polymorbidity remain particularly vulnerable. Therefore, before prescribing biological therapy, a careful risk assessment, appropriate screening, and subsequent dynamic monitoring are necessary [6].

Conclusion. Despite significant progress in rheumatology, many aspects of gout remain unclear. One of the most controversial issues is the appropriateness of drug treatment of asymptomatic hyperuricemia. The available research results do not yet provide convincing evidence of a reduction in cardiovascular risk with early initiation of urate-lowering therapy.

Further development of the field is associated with the implementation of the principles of personalized medicine. It is expected that the choice of therapy in the future will be based not only on the clinical manifestations of the disease, but also on the genetic characteristics of urate transporters, immunological profile and functional state of the kidneys.

An individualized approach will allow selecting the most effective drug combinations and minimizing the risk of side effects. In the future, this may provide a transition from symptom control to full prevention of gout development and its complications at the molecular level.

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